

Data sharing in paediatric clinical research – A protocol (conect4children)

Mariagrazia Felisi¹, Fedele Bonifazi², Maddalena Toma², Claudia Pansieri¹,
Rebecca Leary³, Victoria Hedley³, Ronald Cornet⁴, Giorgio Reggiardo¹,
Annalisa Landi², Steve Canham⁵, Sinéad Nally⁶, Adriana Ceci²

¹ Consorzio per Valutazioni Biologiche e Farmacologiche

² Fondazione per la Ricerca Farmacologica “Gianni Benzi” Onlus

³ Newcastle University

⁴ Amsterdam UMC

⁵ ECRIN

⁶ Novartis Pharma AG

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List of abbreviations:

c4c: conect4children

CTs: clinical trials

EMA: European Medicines Agency

FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable

ICMJE: International Committee of Medical Journal Editors

IMI2-JU: Innovative Medicines Initiative 2 Joint Undertaking

Background

Conducting clinical trials (CTs) in the paediatric population can be difficult due to ethical, regulatory, methodological, and commercial issues influencing many factors such as procedures, sample size, and company strategies. On one hand, the lack of evidence-based research and the unmet medical needs, and on the other hand, the low investment of pharma companies in paediatric research are increasingly promoting the use of existing resources, such as data deriving from CTs especially the ones involving both children and adults, which do not always present the paediatric data separately, and for which the availability of the original data may allow ad hoc analysis¹. Sharing CTs data offer many potential benefits also for people involved in clinical research, who can perform analysis on a large amount of data and obtain useful information without conducting new studies¹⁻⁴.

CTs data sharing is promoted by some eminent organizations like the World Health Organization and the U.S. National Academy of Medicine which published reports asking for responsible sharing of data from CTs. Moreover, the European Medicines Agency (EMA) declared the necessity for data sharing and requested applicants manufacturing drugs and medical devices to share their research data⁵, to reduce the risks of improper sharing, respect individual participants whose data are shared, and increase public trust in CTs and the sharing of CTs data.

In addition, the International Committee of Medical Journal Editors (ICMJE) requires a data sharing plan for CTs that begin enrolling children on or after 1 January 2019, as a condition for publication of a clinical trial report in its member journals⁶. This data sharing plan foreseen by the ICMJE has to indicate whether individual de-identified participant data (including data dictionaries) will be shared; the type of data to be shared; additional documentation available (study protocol, statistical analysis plan, etc); the time of publication and the publication duration; and information on the accessibility conditions (including people having access, the analyses/uses allowed, and modalities of access/sharing)⁶.

In 2006 the EU established a formal step towards the specific therapeutic needs of paediatric population with the Paediatric Regulation (EC) No 1901/2006^{7,8}, which concerns the development of medicinal products for paediatric use, without subjecting the paediatric population to unnecessary clinical trials.

In addition, the Innovative Medicines Initiative 2 Joint Undertaking (IMI2-JU) promoted the project Collaborative Network for European Clinical Trials for Children (conect4children or c4c, <https://conect4children.org/>), Grant Agreement 777389. c4c responds to the urgent need of improving

paediatric clinical research in Europe. Although strongly recommended, a few initiatives sharing CTs data in the paediatric field still exist⁹, and no specific methods or procedures to use these data are already available¹⁰⁻¹¹. The project is based on collaborative work, including interoperable data archiving and knowledge sharing practices, with the aim of filling in the gap of the current, fragmented paediatric clinical trials infrastructure in Europe.

In the framework of Work Package 5 “*Data coordinating center and data quality standards*”, scouting of initiatives (such as platforms, projects, private and public initiatives of pharma industries or no-profit organization, consortium of Sponsors/Funders, databases of pharma industries, or no-profit organization, etc.) sharing CTs data, with a focus on paediatric data, will be performed.

This work aims to scout existing initiatives that are developing/have developed electronic archiving programmes to store, share and reuse data from paediatric CTs and to assess their suitability for sharing paediatric data from industry/not-industry CTs.

Methods

Desk research on existing CTs data sharing initiatives will be conducted through literature database PubMed using the following keywords: “initiative”, “repository”, “platform”, “database”, combined with, “clinical trials data” or “clinical trials documents”, and “paediatric”, and “sharing”. Additional initiatives will be collected from other sources ie: Google, professional contacts, and during meetings. A preliminary search strategy is reported in Annex 1.

Inclusion/Exclusion criteria

Inclusion criteria:

- 1) The initiative has some data coming from paediatric-only trials and/or from trials on paediatric and adult patients.
- 2) The initiative has information publicly available in English.

Exclusion criteria:

- 1) The initiative declares do not have paediatric data and not interested.
- 2) The repositories reporting only aggregate data.

Repositories included will then be analysed and compared through a two-steps process. Firstly, information publicly available will be searched on the initiative’s website and a spreadsheet will be drafted to collect the following information:

General features

- Geographical location of the initiative
- Funding: private or public or public/private sponsor
- Funding: regular/sustained funding and business continuity measures
- Source of CTs data (i.e., non-commercial, commercial sources and both sources)
- Therapeutic area/s currently covered
- Availability of instructions for data owners/data submitters
- Availability of instructions for prospective data users

Data and documents features

- Data “in” standards (e.g., CDISC, SDTM, ADaM, CDASH, other)
- Availability of guidance on data composition/structure/format
- Document content (annotated CRF, study protocol, statistical analysis plan, clinical study report)
- Document content (annotated CRF, study protocol, statistical analysis plan, clinical study report)
- Possibility to download data and analyse outside of the repository platform Standard of data downloaded
- Measures to protect data privacy (anonymisation, pseudonymisation, encryption, aggregation, other)

Paediatric specificity

- Availability of paediatric CTs data
- Possibility to filter information per specific paediatric age-cohort/generic age groups

Legal provisions for uploading and reusing data

- Data access type (direct sharing, controlled access, open access, as defined in the Grant Agreement n. 777389)
- Data accessibility restriction
- Data protection policy available
- Existing Informed consent form allowing data storage and reuse

IT technologies

- Security protocols

The reference persons of the initiatives will be searched through publicly available information and professionals contacts. A questionnaire will be sent in order to better describe the initiatives. Details, such as the number and the type of studies, the ontologies, and format of the documents will be asked.

The suitability of initiatives for sharing data from industry/not-industry CTs will be assessed using a set of purpose-built indicators. Then, two authors independently will rate each initiative by classifying each indicator as ‘satisfied’, ‘partially satisfied’, ‘not satisfied’, ‘information not available’. Discrepancies will be discussed and solved.

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Annex 1

Number	Search string
1	(clinical research data) AND sharing
2	((clinical data[Title] AND sharing[Title]) AND (re-use OR secondary use))
3	((((clinical[Title]) AND data[Title]) AND sharing[Title]) AND (secondary use[Title] OR re-use[Title] OR reuse[Title]))
4	(((((clinical[Title] OR biomedical[Title] OR patient[Title])) AND data) AND sharing) AND (re-use OR re use OR secondary use))
5	(((((clinical[Title] OR biomedical[Title] OR patient[Title])) AND data[Title] AND sharing[Title]) AND (re-use[Title] OR reuse[Title] OR secondary use[Title]))
6	(((((clinical[Title] OR biomedical[Title] OR patient[Title] OR health[Title] OR medical[Title] OR medicine[Title])) AND data) AND sharing) AND (re-use OR reuse OR secondary use))
7	(((((clinical[Title] OR biomedical[Title] OR patient[Title] OR health[Title] OR medical[Title] OR medicine[Title])) AND data[Title] AND sharing[Title]) AND (re-use[Title] OR reuse[Title] OR use[Title] OR secondary use[Title]))
8	((((((clinical[Title] OR biomedical[Title] OR patient[Title] OR health[Title] OR medical[Title] OR medicine[Title])) AND data) AND sharing) AND (re-use OR reuse OR secondary use)))) AND (repositor* OR initiativ*)
10	((((((clinical[Title] OR biomedical[Title] OR patient[Title] OR health[Title] OR medical[Title] OR medicine[Title])) AND data[Title] AND sharing[Title]))) AND (repositor*[Title] OR initiativ*[Title]))
11	((((((clinical[Title] OR biomedical[Title] OR patient[Title] OR health[Title] OR medical[Title] OR medicine[Title])) AND data[Title] AND sharing[Title]))) AND (repositor*[Title])
12	((clinical[Title] OR biomedical[Title] OR patient[Title] OR health[Title] OR medical[Title] OR medicine[Title]) AND data[Title]) AND (repositor*[Title])
13	((clinical[Title] OR biomedical[Title] OR patient[Title] OR health[Title] OR medical[Title] OR medicine[Title]) AND (data[Title]OR document*[Title])) AND repositor*[Title])
14	((clinical OR biomedical OR patient OR health OR medical OR medicine) AND (data OR document*)) AND (repositor*[Title]))
15	((clinical OR biomedical OR patient OR health OR medical OR medicine) AND (data OR document*)) AND (repositor* OR storag*[Title] OR archiv*[Title]))
16	(clinical OR biomedical OR patient OR health OR medical OR medicine) AND (repositor* OR storag*[Title] OR archiv*[Title])
17	(clinical[Title] OR biomedical[Title] OR patient[Title] OR health[Title] OR medical[Title] OR medicine[Title]) AND (repositor* OR storag*[Title] OR archiv*[Title])

18	((clinical[Title] OR biomedical[Title] OR patient[Title] OR health[Title] OR medical[Title] OR medicine[Title]) AND (repositor[Title]* OR storag*[Title] OR archiv*[Title]))
19	(((((clinical OR biomedical OR patient OR health OR medical OR medicine) AND (data OR document*)) AND (repositor*) AND (storag*[Title] OR archiv*[Title]))))
20	clinical trial AND (data OR document*) AND (repositor* OR stor* OR archiv*)
21	(clinical AND trial) AND (data OR document*) AND (repositor*[Title] OR storag*[Title] OR stor*[Title] OR archiv*[Title]))
22	(clinical OR clinical AND trial) AND (data OR document*) AND (repositor*[Title] OR stor*[Title] OR archiv*[Title]))
23	(clinical OR trial OR clinical AND trial) AND (data OR document*) AND (repositor*[Title] OR stor*[Title] OR archiv*[Title]))
24	((clinical OR trial OR clinical AND trial) AND (data OR document*) AND (repositor*[Title] OR stor*[Title] OR archiv*[Title] OR shar*[Title]))
25	(((((clinical OR trial OR clinical AND trial OR biomedical OR patient OR health OR medical OR medicine) AND (data OR document*)) AND (repositor*[Title] OR stor*[Title] OR archiv*[Title] OR shar*[Title]))
26	((data AND ("Clinical Trials as Topic"[Mesh] OR "Clinical Trial" [Publication Type] OR (clinical trial) OR trial OR research))) AND (("data collection"[MeSH Terms] OR "Information Dissemination"[Mesh] OR "Datasets as Topic"[Mesh] OR "Data Curation"[Mesh] OR "Data Warehousing"[Mesh]) OR archive* OR stor* OR reposit*) AND ((secondary use) OR re-use OR reuse OR shar*)
27	((data AND ("Clinical Trials as Topic"[Mesh] OR "Clinical Trial" [Publication Type] OR (clinical trial) OR trial OR research))) AND (("data collection"[MeSH Terms] OR "Information Dissemination"[Mesh] OR "Datasets as Topic"[Mesh] OR "Data Curation"[Mesh] OR "Data Warehousing"[Mesh]) OR archive* OR stor* OR reposit*) AND ((secondary use) OR re-use OR reuse OR shar*) AND (child* OR paediatric* OR pediatric*)
28	((data OR document) AND ("Clinical Trials as Topic"[Mesh] OR "Clinical Trial" [Publication Type] OR (clinical trial) OR trial OR research))) AND (("data collection"[MeSH Terms] OR "Information Dissemination"[Mesh] OR "Datasets as Topic"[Mesh] OR "Data Curation"[Mesh] OR "Data Warehousing"[Mesh]) OR archive* OR stor* OR reposit*) AND ((secondary use) OR re-use OR reuse OR shar*) AND (child* OR paediatric* OR pediatric*)
29	((data OR document) AND ("Clinical Trials as Topic"[Mesh] OR "Clinical Trial" [Publication Type] OR (clinical trial) OR trial))) AND (("data collection"[MeSH Terms] OR "Information Dissemination"[Mesh] OR "Datasets as Topic"[Mesh] OR "Data Curation"[Mesh] OR "Data Warehousing"[Mesh]) OR archive* OR stor* OR reposit*) AND ((secondary use) OR re-use OR reuse OR shar*) AND (child* OR paediatric* OR pediatric*)

30	((data OR document) AND ("Clinical Trials as Topic"[Mesh] OR "Clinical Trial" [Publication Type] OR (clinical trial) OR trial) AND (drug OR medicine*)) AND (child* OR paediatric* OR pediatric*) AND (("data collection"[MeSH Terms] OR "Information Dissemination"[Mesh] OR "Datasets as Topic"[Mesh] OR "Data Curation"[Mesh] OR "Data Warehousing"[Mesh]) OR archive* OR stor* OR reposit*) AND ((secondary use) OR re-use OR reuse OR shar*)
31	((data OR document) AND ("Clinical Trials as Topic"[Mesh] OR "Clinical Trial" [Publication Type] OR (clinical trial) OR trial) AND (drug OR medicine*)) AND (child* OR paediatric* OR pediatric*) AND (("data collection"[MeSH Terms] OR "Information Dissemination"[Mesh] OR "Datasets as Topic"[Mesh] OR "Data Curation"[Mesh] OR "Data Warehousing"[Mesh]) OR archiv* OR storage* OR storing OR reposit*) AND ((secondary use) OR re-use OR reuse OR share OR sharing)
32	((data OR document) AND ((clinical trial) OR trial) AND (drug OR medicine*)) AND (child* OR paediatric* OR pediatric*) AND (("data collection"[MeSH Terms] OR "Information Dissemination"[Mesh] OR "Datasets as Topic"[Mesh] OR "Data Curation"[Mesh] OR "Data Warehousing"[Mesh]) OR archiv* OR storage* OR storing OR reposit*) AND ((secondary use) OR re-use OR reuse OR share OR sharing)
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34	(clinical OR trial OR clinical AND trial) AND (data OR document*) AND (repositor*[Title] OR stor*[Title] OR archiv*[Title]))